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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VIb.

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In NDAC/LO/107 (Paper VIa), a number of further tests of the STDDBL solution program were envisaged. Some of these have now been performed, with results as reported below. The number of interesting parameters to vary is large, and the CPU-times for simulation/solution long (typically 1-2 hours per system), thus one may profitably go on testing for a long time. For STDDBL, however, such testing must now be postponed in favour of development work on the other DS reduction programs.

1. Optimization of g and $C\chi$

In the runs reported in Paper VIa, the Input Catalogue position of the primary star was at a fix offset from its true position. In the present runs, I have assumed instead a gaussian spread of errors, with the (somewhat large) $\sigma = 1$ arcsec in each coordinate. In this way, the mean position-offset is about 1.3 arcsec, but with occasional values in the 3-4 arcsec range. The real distribution will hopefully be somewhat narrower ($\sigma = 0.5-0.75$ arcsec), but outliers of at least the present size must be allowed for. For the *relative* position of the secondary, I use a single-coordinate $\sigma = 0.1$ arcsec. (This is maybe too optimistic, and some tests with a higher value are described in Section 5). As for the double star parameters, I have randomized the separation, magnitude difference and position on the sky, but always with the primary star magnitude $H_{pr} = 8.5$. Ser. A (single IFOV-pointing at photocentre) consists of 340 systems with separations between 0.2 and 10 arcsec (uniform distribution over $\lg sep$), magnitude differences between 0 and 4, and a uniform distribution over the sky. To this may be added Ser. A1 with an additional 60 systems (separations 0.62-1.25 arcsec) where there is also a linear decrease of the IDT sensitivity with time (cf. Section 4 below). Ser. B (individual IFOV pointing), finally, consists of 100 systems with separations between 10 and 30 arcsec.

First, in order to estimate a good $C\chi_a$ -limit, a mesh-point in the *a priori* solution was placed artificially at a given distance from the true primary position. For a subset of 25 runs from the A-series, the results are rather clearcut. When the mesh-point is more than 0.6 arcsec from the true position, virtually *all* solutions fail, and S_a is always larger than about 50. When it is less than 0.3 arcsec from the primary, all solutions converge, with S_a -values typically below 10. In the 0.4-0.5 arcsec middle range there is some ambiguity, with several converged solutions having S_a above 200. The gain from increasing $C\chi_a$ above 50 would thus probably be offset by the larger number of 'false' *a priori* solutions, and for Ser. A and A1, I have used $C\chi_a = 50$. A similar investigation for the B-series is qualitatively similar, but the dividing S_a -value is now closer to 25, and this is thus taken as the $C\chi_a$ -value in Ser B.

The other parameter to vary is the mesh-spacing g in 'round 1' of the solutions. As expected from naïve considerations about the distribution of primary star distance to the nearest mesh-point, and about solution success with respect to this

distance, there is an optimum g around 0.7 arcsec. A too small g gives certain convergence at some mesh-point, but many points have to be tried. A too large g gives convergence in fewer points (scaling inversely with g^2), but the solution may be completely missed, with no mesh-point close enough to the true primary position. Such cases have then to be tried again in the 'follow-up' part of solutions with smaller g (=0.55 arcsec in the present runs). The mean number of mesh-points tried will be minimal somewhere in between. The results in Table 1 depend of course on the assumed *a priori* errors, but they show the principle quite well. It is clear from these figures that a too small g may be wasteful of CPU-time, but otherwise, the exact value is not critical. (The smaller *nmesh*-values in Ser. B seem significant and in line with the smaller $C\chi_a$).

Table 1. Mean number of mesh-points tried in the *a prio* solutions for the primary star position, for different values of g . A is for 400 systems with separation less than 10 arcsec, B is for 100 systems with larger separation (individual IFOV-pointing), and CPU is the mean HP9000 CPU-time per system for Ser. A and B together.

g (arcs)	<i>nmesh</i> (A)	<i>nmesh</i> (B)	CPU(min)
0.60	17	15	12.6
0.70	15	12	10.6
0.80	16	10	10.9

2. Astrometric solution results

The present runs constitute the largest uniform set of 'STDDBL'-solutions available, and it is interesting to make some simple statistics for the astrometric and photometric errors. Ideally, one would like to have these statistics for rather small bins in separation, magnitude-difference and ecliptic latitude, but then the number of stars in each bin becomes small, and the statistical errors correspondingly large. I have chosen instead to assume that the variations with these parameters are *independent* of each other, and that it is thus sufficient to study the marginal distributions when one at a time is varied. Tables 2a-c shows the mean astrometric errors as function of separation, ecliptic latitude and magnitude difference.

Table 2a. Mean astrometric errors (mas) for the primary and the secondary star, as function of the separation. Also given are the mean number of FOV-crossings, the mean normalized fit to the observations (S_f), and the $Se1$ and Ser χ^2 -fits. All 500 solutions are used, and the values in parentheses are the statistical errors in the means.

sep(arcs)	n	nfov	S_f	rms1	rms2	$Se1$	Ser
0.2-0.4	65	152(8)	1.08(.01)	1.32(.11)	9.2(1.6)	6.9(0.6)	6.7(0.6)
0.4-0.8	87	146(6)	1.06(.01)	1.05(.05)	8.3(1.0)	8.3(0.6)	4.7(0.3)
0.8-1.2	70	155(6)	1.06(.01)	0.93(.05)	5.9(0.9)	6.8(0.7)	4.8(0.4)
1.2-3.0	84	145(6)	1.06(.01)	1.01(.07)	8.1(0.9)	6.4(0.4)	5.4(0.5)
3.0-10	94	143(5)	1.02(.01)	1.02(.04)	8.7(1.5)	7.1(0.6)	5.7(0.5)
10-30	100	148(6)	0.84(.01)	1.24(.05)	12.3(1.2)	6.4(0.4)	5.5(0.4)
all	500	148(3)	1.01(.01)	1.09(.03)	8.9(0.5)	7.0(0.2)	5.4(0.2)

Table 2b. Mean astrometric errors and *Se*-fits, as function of the (absolute) ecliptic latitude.

eclat(deg)	n	nfov	Sf	rms1	rms 2	Se1	Ser
0-11	103	96(2)	1.01(.01)	1.43(.08)	11.0(1.3)	6.7(0.5)	5.6(0.4)
11-22	105	113(2)	1.01(.01)	1.26(.06)	11.4(1.5)	7.1(0.6)	5.8(0.5)
22-37	93	142(4)	1.01(.01)	1.12(.04)	8.6(0.8)	7.3(0.5)	4.9(0.4)
37-55	97	225(6)	1.02(.01)	0.88(.03)	6.9(0.8)	8.1(0.6)	6.1(0.4)
55-90	102	168(1)	1.01(.01)	0.75(.03)	6.5(0.7)	5.8(0.4)	4.8(0.4)
all	500	148(3)	1.01(.01)	1.09(.03)	8.9(0.5)	7.0(0.2)	5.4(0.2)

Table 2c. Mean astrometric errors and *Se*-fits, as function of the magnitude difference.

dm(mag)	n	nfov	Sf	rms1	rms2	Se1	Ser
0-0.8	108	149(6)	1.03(.01)	1.30(.07)	1.7(0.1)	6.8(0.5)	4.8(0.4)
0.8-1.6	100	146(6)	1.01(.01)	1.07(.05)	3.4(0.2)	6.2(0.5)	5.8(0.4)
1.6-2.4	111	143(5)	1.00(.01)	1.07(.05)	5.6(0.3)	7.4(0.6)	5.0(0.3)
2.4-3.2	80	152(6)	1.00(.01)	1.01(.06)	12.4(1.2)	7.2(0.5)	6.0(0.5)
3.2-4.0	101	150(6)	1.01(.01)	0.98(.04)	23.0(1.5)	7.2(0.5)	5.7(0.5)
all	500	148(3)	1.01(.01)	1.09(.03)	8.9(0.5)	7.0(0.2)	5.4(0.2)

From the variations in these three tables, one may put together the full variation of the astrometric accuracy with *sep*, *dm* and *eclat*, for this special case $H_{pr}=8.5$. From Table 2a, it is seen that the mean astrometric error varies rather little with separation. For the closest systems, the individual star errors increase (but the photocentric error remains constant, cf. NDAC/LO/071). For the wide systems with individual pointing, the errors are also increased, but generally less than 25-50%. Table 2b shows the well-known variation with ecliptic latitude. For latitudes less than some 50 degrees, the error-decrease with latitude corresponds roughly to the expectation from the increased number of FOV-crossings, but for the high-latitude stars, there is a genuine improvement due to the favourable distribution of scan-angles. Table 2c, finally, shows the increasing error for the secondary component as its magnitude increases. In all the tables, the Se_1 - and Se_r -values show mostly 'random' variations, and their general mean values 7.0 and 5.4 are close to those obtained in Paper VIa. (This means that one may use the formal mean errors as a measure of the true uncertainty of a solution, only increasing those for the primary component by some 20%).

3. Photometric solution results

In Paper VIa, I discussed preliminarily the systematic errors in the photometric results. With the more extensive statistics now available, this discussion can now be more conclusive. For the primary magnitudes, the only important parameter is the colour of the star. Using all 500 solutions, the regression line (cf. Fig 2 in Paper VIa) has the equation

$$dm_1 = -0.041 + 0.084 * col \quad (1)$$

The slope and intercept are close to the expected ones, and the residual spread is actually *smaller* than expected (0.8 times the formal mean error).

For the relative magnitudes, there is *no* colour term, but instead a more complex dependence on separation and magnitude difference. Using only first- and second-order terms in sep and dm , a reasonably good fit for the systematic $d(dm)$ -values (in the range $0.6 < sep < 10$ arcsec, $dm < 4$ mag) is

$$d(dm) = -0.003 * sep + 0.0006 * sep^2 + 0.0078 * sep * dm \quad (2)$$

which diminishes the error from 3.2 times the formal estimate to 1.7 times. The main term is the last one, and the simple

$$d(dm) = 0.0082 * sep * dm \quad (3)$$

is almost as good (mean error 1.8 times the formal one). Interestingly, the closest doubles (where one would expect some problems) show *no* systematic $d(dm)$ -trend, and the same is true for the wide ones with individual IFOV-pointing. Here, the solution dm -values have mean errors that are only about 40% above the formal ones, and no simple dependences on sep or dm can be discerned.

The above results for $d(dm)$ are somewhat at variance with those given in Table 5 of Paper VIa, but being based on a larger number of solutions, the present relations are probably more realistic. The main point is that systematic errors like eqs. (1) and (3) are to be expected in the STDDBL photometric results, and that careful calibrations therefore have to be done after the reductions, using ground-based dm -determinations.

4. Influence of IDT sensitivity variations

In most of the present runs, as well as in all previous ones, the general IDT-sensitivity is assumed to be constant over the whole mission. As long as the real time-variation is *known* and applied in the reductions, no extra problems are expected, but to make sure I introduced in the 'A1'-simulations a linear trend amounting to 0.2 magnitudes/year. Calibrating this sensitivity-variation in the solution programs restored the 'constant sensitivity' assumption, and no further problems were found.

Problems *do* appear, however, when the sensitivity-calibration is erroneous or uncertain. As a rough model of a 'systematic error', I have introduced a calibration sensitivity-slope differing by s_s from the true one. Similarly, to give a 'random' error, I introduced a gaussian error (zero mean, spread sig_s) in the IDT sensitivity at each FOV-crossing. The 'final' (excluding the mesh-search) solutions for Ser. A and B above were repeated with non-zero values for s_s and sig_s , giving a series of new results. As a measure of the error-increases, Table 3 lists mean Se_1 and Se_r parameters for three different separation-ranges.

Table 3. Mean Se_1 and Ser -values, for three different ranges of sep , as function of ss and sig_s .

$ss(\text{mag/yr})$	$sig_s(\text{mag})$	sep=0.3-0.6		sep=0.6-10		sep=10-30	
		Se1	Ser	Se1	Ser	Se1	Ser
0.00	0.00	7.0	5.4	7.0	5.3	6.4	5.5
0.01	0.00	7.2	6.9	7.4	6.6	6.4	5.6
0.02	0.00	7.8	12.	7.9	9.2	6.4	6.1
0.03	0.00	8.8	21.	8.6	13.	6.5	7.0
0.00	0.02	7.1	6.3	7.2	5.9	6.4	5.6
0.00	0.03	7.4	7.4	7.2	6.4	6.4	5.8
0.00	0.05	8.4	11.	7.5	8.3	6.5	6.3
0.00	0.10	15.	30.	9.1	19.	6.9	9.2

Generally, the relative errors are more sensitive than the primary star ones, and generally, a systematic error is much more serious than a random one. There is also a large difference between the 'normal' values for $sep=0.6-10$ arcsec, and those for smaller or larger separations. The data in Table 3 may be fitted by simple quadratic relations

$$\begin{aligned} Se_1 &= Se_1(0) [1 + a_1(s_s/0.01)^2 + b_1(sig_s/0.01)^2] \\ Se_r &= Se_r(0) [1 + a_r(s_s/0.01)^2 + b_r(sig_s/0.01)^2] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

with the following coefficients:

sep(arcs)	a_1	b_1	a_r	b_r
0.3-0.6	0.029	0.010	0.31	0.044
0.6-10	0.027	0.003	0.17	0.025
10-30	0.002	0.001	0.03	0.007

We see that a 10% error-increase in the relative data (20% in Se_r) is obtained 'normally' with $s_s=0.01$ mag/yr or $sig_s=0.03$ mag. The primary star data are less sensitive, and about 3 times larger sensitivity errors are needed to give the same astrometric error increase. For larger separations (individual IFOV-pointing), the primary data are very insensitive, but the 10% relative error-increase is now obtained with $s_s=0.03$ mag/yr or $sig_s=0.05$ mag. For smaller separations, on the other hand, the same increase comes already at $s_s=0.01$ or $sig_s=0.02$. (The problems get even worse as the separations are further diminished, and with $sig_s=0.10$ mag, almost no solutions were obtained for separations less than 0.25 arcsec).

These data show clearly that the general IDT sensitivity has to be calibrated carefully throughout the mission. For single stars, this is mainly useful for photometric purposes, but for doubles and multiples the astrometry is affected rather strongly. (The sig_s -tolerance should also be representative of the acceptable magnitude-errors for multiples with one or more variable components. Generally, typical visual magnitude estimates are *not* sufficiently accurate, and photoelectric monitoring is required in order to preserve the full astrometric accuracy).

5. Tests with poorer a priori knowledge

As stated in Section 1, all the simulations so far had a *relative* $\sigma=0.1$ arcsec. In order to have some feeling for the influence of a higher value, I have made two smaller series of runs ('A2' with 64 systems from 0.3 to 10 arcsec separation, 'B2' with 25 systems from 10 to 30 arcsec) with 0.2 arcsec σ instead. Again putting a mesh-point at a given distance from the *a priori* position, the $C\chi_a$ -value for the A2 series seemed to need a downward revision to around 20. (Far from a mesh-point, the S_a -values are generally higher than before, but at 0.4-0.5 arcsec from the true position, there are some false solutions with $S_a=10-20$). For the B2 series, no such problems are encountered. From similar tests with the mesh-point at the true primary position, it is clear also that it is very difficult to have a solution when the total relative error is above some 0.5 arcsec.

The above conclusions were tested by running the standard mesh-search with parameters given in Table 4. Interestingly, *all* the non-converged or false solutions are for the four systems with actual relative errors above 0.50 arcsec, and the mean number of mesh-points given are for the other 61+24 systems. Contrary to the preliminary decision, there is in reality no need to decrease $C\chi_a$. Any extra false mesh-solutions are caught by the $C\chi_f$ -limit, and the mean number of mesh-points

is lower with the original $C\chi_a$. The optimum mesh-spacing is probably decreased, however, as can be seen by comparison with Table 1.

Table 4. Mean number of mesh-points tried in the *a prio* solutions for the primary star position, for different values of g and $C\chi_a$. A is for 61 systems with separation less than 10 arcsec, B for 24 systems with larger separation (individual IFOV-pointing).

runs	$g(\text{arcs})$	$C\chi_a$	nmesh
A	0.60	20	20
A	0.60	50	17
A	0.70	50	19
B	0.60	25	22
B	0.70	25	19

The main conclusion from the A2/B2 runs is that the mesh-search works quite well even with the larger σ . The real problems come only for relative errors above 0.5 arcsec, and such cases will hopefully be identified and remeasured (from the ground) well before the start of the DS reductions.

6. Conclusions

The results of the present tests show again that the main parts of 'STDDBL' are working as intended. The Input/Output parts are not yet written, but the possible problems are more 'administrative' and may be postponed for some time yet. (The output format(s) have to be discussed, however, because there is no obvious single description useful for *all* systems). Work will now be started on 'STDMUL' and 'SEEKDBL', which are the other 'main' solution programs.